

Semantic integration of information about orthologs and diseases: The OGO system

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Abstract

Semantic Web technologies have been successfully applied to biological and medical domains in the last few years. Most approaches are based on translating existing thesauri into ontologies. Even though this allows for the (partial) formalization of the knowledge, the advanced capabilities of ontologies are not completely exploited. In this work, we present a resource, the OGO system, that exploits Semantic Web technologies to integrate information regarding orthologous sequences and genetic diseases, also ensuring consistency and avoiding redundancy, and therefore easing the labour of life science researchers. The query interface provides a mechanism to define semantic queries exploiting advanced functionalities from ontologies, maintaining the user-friendly settings of general query systems.

1. Introduction

Life sciences is a knowledge based discipline, in which the production of knowledge from data (e.g. the cellular location of a gene product) is a daily activity. However, such knowledge is represented through vast amounts of complex and changing information stored in disparate resources Bodenreider and Stevens (2006) and in machine-unfriendly formats like natural language

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annotations or scientific literature Attwood et al. (2009). Consequently, the efficient management of such knowledge is paramount for advancing research in life sciences Antezana et al. (2009a), and this goal requires such knowledge to be integrated *for* humans and not *by* humans. Life scientists waste a lot of time trying to find the inter-related information, and manually removing the redundancy of the results obtained from querying different, independent information resources. In addition to this, the results provided by most of the currently available repositories are complete records rather than the concrete information units of interest for the users.

Orthologous sequences, or simply orthologs, are different copies of the same genetic sequence, present in different species that appeared as a result of evolutionary divergence. Nowadays, each orthology repository provides clusters of orthologous genes, which are obtained in different ways and for which several details are provided. Thus, having access to the information from those resources in an integrated way would be very useful for life scientists, as demonstrated by our previous work Miñarro Gimenez et al. (2009). Orthology information is mainly used in phylogenetic studies and for taxonomic classification Wu et al. (2006), but it is used also to generate new hypotheses; it is likely that an ortholog of a given sequence, being in another taxon, has the same function of that sequence Antezana et al. (2009b). Therefore, orthologs are used in research about genetic diseases, in particular for understanding their genetic causes Harvey et al. (2003). However, resources that produce and store orthologous clusters, that is, groups of related orthologs, like OrthoMCL¹, do not offer that information linked to genetic disease and, consequently, the user needs to manually integrate those two kinds of information by using different tools and interfaces.

Nowadays, biomedical researchers need to perform a series of mainly manual tasks to retrieve this kind of translational information. For instance, retrieving the genes related to those that cause **Prostate cancer**, requires taking these actions: (1) query the Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man resource (OMIM²) for obtaining information about the genes that cause **Prostate cancer**; (2) query the existing orthology information resources, such as KOG Tatusov et al. (2003), Inparanoid Remm et al. (2001), Or-

¹<http://orthomcl.org>

²<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/omim/>

thoMCL and Homogene³ for obtaining the orthologous genes; and (3) manual combination and analysis of the information retrieved from all orthology resources. An improvement for the second step is the use of resources such as YOGY Penkett et al. (2006). Consequently, biomedical researchers cannot find easily this information because they are required to know: (1) which resources are available and contain the desired information; (2) how such resources can be accessed and queried; (3) the meaning of the data types and fields used in each resource. The last issue is very important, since it implies that biomedical researchers have to be capable of identifying whether the same types of data coming from the different resources refer to the same real entities. An incorrect interpretation at this level may invalidate any further analysis performed by the researcher. Therefore, there is clear need for methods and tools that help researchers in finding the right information.

One of the most promising endeavours for dealing with such knowledge management problem is the Semantic Web⁴. The Semantic Web is a vision for the next generation web, driven by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C⁵) that advocates for a web made of data, rather than documents. In such ideal web, the data would be published in a machine processable manner, allowing, for example, automated reasoning over different resources to retrieve the needed information item, and only the needed one. The application of the Semantic Web on life sciences is steadily growing, through the so called Life Sciences Semantic Web (LSSW) Good and Wilkinson (2006); Rutenberg et al. (2007); Antezana et al. (2009a). The LSSW is based on the use of Semantic Web oriented W3C standards like RDF⁶ (Resource Description Framework), SPARQL⁷ (SPARQL Query Language for RDF) and OWL⁸ (Web Ontology Language) to codify biological knowledge on a distributed and machine-friendly fashion, in Knowledge Bases (KBs) and bio-ontologies (ontologies that represent biological knowledge). An ontology is a computational representation, using a logical formalism, of a domain of discourse: it provides a collection of formally defined concepts and their relationships so that a reasoner such as Pellet Sirin et al. (2007) or FaCT++ Tsarkov and

³<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/homologene>

⁴<http://www.w3.org/2001/sw/>

⁵<http://www.w3.org/>

⁶<http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-primer/>

⁷<http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query/>

⁸<http://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-overview/>

Horrocks (2006) may automatically operate over such collection. Besides, automated reasoning is mainly used for consistency checking, queries, and classification of new facts against the ontology. A substantial (and growing) group of current KBs and bio-ontologies exploits the LSSW approach, like BioGateway Antezana et al. (2009c), OBI Courtot et al. (2008), Bio2RDF Belleau et al. (2008), and many more (see Antezana et al. (2009a) for a review).

In this paper, we present the new version of our Ontological Gene Orthology (OGO) system Miñarro Gimenez et al. (2009). In OGO, Semantic Web technologies assist life scientists in the development of ortholog/genetic diseases research paths by providing a precise, explicit meaning for information units and intertwining such information. The first version of the OGO system exploited Semantic Web technologies to integrate and manage orthologs information from different resources. The work presented in this paper has improved the OGO system in the following ways. First, the semantic infrastructure has gone through major changes: (1) addition of knowledge about genetic diseases; (2) reuse of existing bio-ontologies. Consequently, the new semantic infrastructure has more knowledge, higher quality and facilitates the interoperability with external resources. Therefore, researchers do not need to be aware any more of the internal structure and meaning of the data types coming from different resources, since this task is provided by the OGO system. Second, we have developed a semantics-guided, user-defined query interface, which permits the design of queries that exploit the semantics of the OGO ontology.

The overall structure and the methodology followed for building the OGO system are briefly reviewed in the beginning of Section 2. Section 3 presents the repository obtained in this work and also the web interfaces developed for querying the OGO knowledge base (OGO KB). Section 3.1 describes the detailed structure and semantics of the OGO KB. Finally, in section 4 we discuss the issues mentioned in this paper and summarize the conclusion reached on the OGO system.

2. Methods

The OGO system consists of three elements: (1) an ontology about orthologs and genetic diseases (the OGO ontology), (2) a KB that stores information of orthologs and related genetic diseases using such ontology as

Figure 1: General structure of the OGO system.

a schema (the OGO KB), and (3) a web interface to access the system⁹ (Figure 1). The OGO ontology is used as a scaffold to integrate information from different resources in the KB. The information is collected from orthologs databases (KOG, Inparanoid, OrthoMCL and Homologene) and the human genetic diseases database (OMIM). The integration of the information sources allows to relate the genes involved in a particular genetic disorder to their orthologs clusters. In order to extend the first version of the OGO system with the genetic disorder resource, we applied the following methodology:

1. Analysis and conceptualization of OMIM (Section 2.1)
2. Extension of the OGO ontology by including OMIM knowledge (Section 2.2).
3. Standardization of the OGO ontology by reusing existing ontologies (Section 2.3).
4. Definition of the mapping rules between OMIM data and the extended OGO ontology for making the data integration an automatic process (Section 2.4).

⁹<http://miuras.inf.um.es/~ogo>

2.1. Analysis and conceptualization of OMIM

The OMIM repository consists of several files (see Table 1): `genemap`, `morbiditymap`, `genetable` and `pubmed_cited`. The `genemap` file describes the cytogenetic locations of genes; the chromosome location, the genes related to the genetic disorder, the status of the OMIM disorder record and the OMIM identifier were able to be annotated from it. The `morbiditymap` file contains an alphabetical list of diseases in which each element in the list identifies a disease and references to other related OMIM records (linked genetic disease information can be extracted from this file). The `genetable` file relates gene names and synonyms to the OMIM record identifiers. Finally, the `pubmed_cited` file contains a list of PubMed citations related to OMIM records. The result of this analysis is the conceptualization shown in Figure 2.

File name	Description	Version	Example
<code>genemap</code>	Cytogenetic locations of genes	28/07/09	16.371 11 25 08 16q22.3-q23.1 ZFX3,ATBF1 C Zinc finger homeobox 3 104155 A, D Prostate cancer,susceptibility to, 176807 (3) 8(ATbf1) 16q22.3-q23.1: Chromosomes location ZFX3, ATBF1: Genes related to the disorder C: Status (confirmed) 104155: OMIM identifier
<code>genemap.key</code>	Fields and methods used in <code>genemap</code>	19/05/09	
<code>morbiditymap</code>	An alphabetical list of diseases	19/05/09	Prostate cancer, susceptibility to, 176807 (3) ZFX3,ATBF1 104155 16q22.3-q23.1 176807: Reference to other related OMIM record ZFX3, ATBF1: Genes related to the disorder 104155: OMIM identifier 16q22.3-q23.1: Chromosomes location
<code>genetable</code>	An alphabetical list of genes relate records	29/05/09	tbf1 104155 tbf1: Gene name 104155: OMIM identifier
<code>pubmed_cited</code>	List of PubMed articles related to records	29/05/09	104155 1719379 104155: OMIM identifier 1719379: PubMed article reference

Table 1: Overall description of the data files of OMIM

2.2. Extension of the OGO ontology with OMIM knowledge

The previous conceptualization was then compared with the OGO ontology, in order to extend it with the knowledge needed for linking the genetic disease information from OMIM to the biological information of the first version of the OGO KB. This process was manually done given the size of the OMIM conceptualization. The results of this step are described next.

Disorders have been included into the new OGO ontology, since they must be linked to already existing orthologs clusters (Figure 2). In the new OGO ontology, two main parts can be distinguished: genetic disorders and orthologs clusters.

Figure 2: The extended OGO ontology.

The main concept in this section is **Disorder**, which represents human genetic disorder of OMIM and is defined through the following properties:

- Name: the name of the disorder, which is unique and compulsory.
- OmimID: unique identifier of the record in OMIM repository, which is unique and compulsory.
- DisorderReference: links to related disorders, if any.
- Location: chromosomal location of the disorder, which is unique and compulsory.

The **Disorder** class is also connected to other classes in the ontology through the following relations (Figure 2):

- causedBy: the gene that causes the genetic disorder, which is compulsory.
- connectedTo: connections between genetic disorders, if any.
- hasMethod: how the genes were associated with the genetic diseases (*e.g.* Deductions from the amino acid sequence of proteins). Genetic diseases are connected to at least one method through this relation.

- `relatedArticle`: references to research papers related to human genetic disorder. The `Article` concept contains the identifier which is used by OMIM for referencing such article. The articles are the ones included in OMIM as Pubmed citations.

The clusters of orthologs are individuals of the class `Cluster`. The orthologs themselves are added as individuals of the class `Gene` and connected to the cluster of orthologs that they belong to through the relationship `hasOrthologous` (Figure 2).

2.3. Standardization of the OGO ontology

The OGO ontology imports¹⁰ other life sciences resources to inter-relate and reuse the knowledge from those resources, in order to increase the standardization of the knowledge contained in the system and to facilitate the data and knowledge interoperability. For this purpose, some ontologies in OBO format have been reused. The natural translation of ontologies in OBO format¹¹ (GO, ECO, NCBI) into OWL treats OBO format terms like classes, not like individuals Tirmizi et al. (2009); Egana et al. (2007); Golbreich et al. (2007). However, the OGO system stores entities such as genes and proteins as individuals. This means that we need to be able to refer to these entities as classes or individuals depending on the context of use. To this end, OWL punning was used in GO, ECO and NCBI¹². Punning can be used to give the same URI to different entities. Therefore, by adding an individual with the same URI to every class of GO, ECO and NCBI, we could refer to such classes as values (*i.e.* as OWL individuals) or as proper OWL classes. For example, in GOA associations like `CYC4 participates_in cell_cycle`, both `CYC4` and `cell_cycle` are OWL individuals. However, `cell_cycle` is also an OWL class.

2.3.1. Reused (imported) ontologies

Gene Ontology (GO): GO Consortium (2000) consists of three ontologies that cover the cellular component, molecular function and biological process domains. Each domain is defined as a GO aspect. These

¹⁰<http://www.w3.org/TR/2009/REC-owl2-syntax-20091027/#Imports>

¹¹<http://www.geneontology.org/GO.format.shtml>

¹²<http://www.w3.org/TR/2009/REC-owl2-new-features-20091027/#Simplemetamodellingcapabilities>

ontologies facilitate the annotation of genes and gene products. Orthologs can be associated with GO terms via GOA (Gene Ontology Annotation) associations Camon et al. (2004). Therefore, the conceptualization of the previous OGO ontology was improved by removing the `GO_Aspect` concept as a separate concept but belonging to the hierarchy of GO terms. Thus, GO was imported into the OGO ontology through the `GO_term` concept, which acts as root concept for GO.

Evidence Codes Ontology (ECO): The GOA associations are qualified with evidence codes (*e.g.* `Inferred from Physical Interaction`, `Inferred from Genomic Context`, *etc.*). ECO¹³ provides a hierarchy of evidence codes, where `ECO_0000000` is the root concept, allowing querying of GOA associations *via* their evidence code types (*e.g.* a scientist may be only interested in GOA associations inferred from genomic context). Thus, the previous `Evidence_Code` concept in the OGO ontology was replaced by `ECO_0000000`. However, the `hasEvidenceCode` relationship was not changed.

NCBI taxonomy database (NCBI): The NCBI taxonomy Sayers et al. (2009) represents the taxonomical classification of organisms. In order to include the taxonomical hierarchies leading to the organisms of interest, portions of the database had to be converted to OWL. The ontological representation of biological species, and specially their classification in taxonomical ranks (genus, order, *etc.*) is still an open problem Schulz et al. (2008), due to the metamodelling nature of the biological taxonomical classification. In the case of OGO, we opted for the simplest solution, that is, codifying each taxon as an OWL class and creating a subsumption hierarchy (*e.g.* `Tetrapoda` is a subclass of `Sarcopterygii` in the OGO ontology), as this strategy was the least complex axiomatically. However, it should be noted that it is not a completely rigorous ontological representation. The import of this taxonomical classification has changed the ontology by means of the replacement of previous `Species` concept to `NCBI_1` concept as ontology root.

Relationship Ontology (RO): RO Smith et al. (2005) was created in order to provide a common set of relationships for bio-ontologies, to fa-

¹³<http://www.obofoundry.org/cgi-bin/detail.cgi?id=evidencecode>

Facilitate integration of the knowledge present in them (*e.g.* the `is-a` relationship is semantically equivalent in GO and in the Cell Type Ontology (CL) Bard et al. (2005)). The OGO ontology imports two RO relationships, namely `participates_in` and `located_in` (`gene_product participates_in some (molecular_function or biological_process)` and `gene_product located_in some cellular_component`). The rest of the needed relationships were added to the system manually, as they were not available in RO. However, relationships similar or related to the ones tailored for OGO by us have already been proposed in the RO community, even though they are still not present in the stable version of RO¹⁴.

GO belongs to the OBO foundry Smith et al. (2007), *i.e.* it is a reference bio-ontology that fulfils the OBO foundry criteria¹⁵. ECO and RO are candidate OBO foundry ontologies. The NCBI taxonomy is not a bio-ontology *per se*, but it can be translated into OWL in a relatively straight way. Other improvements performed on the first version of the OGO ontology are described as follows. The **Reference** class was removed and its information was integrated into the **Name** and **Identifier** properties of gene and protein concepts for clarity. In addition, the previous `fixProtein` relationship was replaced to `isTranslatedTo` for accuracy. These changes have improved the quality of the OGO ontology, adding new knowledge through the imported resources and making the modeling more clear.

2.3.2. Implementation

The OGO ontology was defined in OWL with Protégé¹⁶, a free, open source ontology editor and knowledge framework. OWL was chosen for the OGO system due to its balance between expressive power and decidability, allowing the application of automated reasoning. The consistency of the OGO ontology was checked using Pellet. Also, OWL was designed as part of the Semantic Web Stack¹⁷, allowing the reuse of external knowledge *via* URIs (in the case of the OGO system, GO, ECO, NCBI, and RO).

¹⁴See, for example http://www.bioontology.org/wiki/index.php/RO:Main_Page#Proposed_homologous_to_relation

¹⁵<http://www.obofoundry.org/crit.shtml>

¹⁶<http://protege.stanford.edu/>

¹⁷http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Semantic_Web_Stack

RDF is also part of the Semantic Web stack, and therefore an OWL (RDF/XML) ontology can be accessed with RDF tools, facilitating the use of both languages in a system like OGO. RDF offers the possibility of executing queries with SPARQL. The JENA Semantic Web Framework¹⁸ was used for creating instances and querying the model through SPARQL queries. JENA is an open source Java framework for building Semantic Web applications, that allows to handle OWL (RDF/XML) ontologies with persistent storage and provides a SPARQL query engine. The persistency was implemented in a MySQL¹⁹ database: instances were stored as RDF triples in the database.

Finally, the OGO ontology definitions, stored in the OWL file `OGO.owl`, can be downloaded from the ontology library²⁰, including the imported ontologies ECO (`eco_punned.owl`), GO (`go_punned.owl`), NCBI (`ncbi_punned.owl`) and RO (`ro.owl`).

2.4. Mappings between the OGO ontology and OMIM

This process requires the definition of mapping rules between the OGO ontology and OMIM. Such rules are used for mapping the data contained in the OMIM files onto their corresponding classes, properties and relationships in the OGO ontology. Once the OGO ontology has been extended to include the knowledge about genetic disorders, the correspondences between the OMIM files and the ontological entities were defined for making the integration of data automatic. The OMIM record number plays an important role in this task, as it can be used to navigate through the different OMIM files, and generate complete, conceptual OMIM records. Each item is connected to the same genetic disorder instance by its OMIM identifier. Besides, each file provides different data fields accounting for the relations and properties of the genetic disorder. Figure 3 depicts how the fields from OMIM files are mapped to the concepts of the OGO ontology. Once the mapping rules have been defined, the automated integration process can be launched.

Data and knowledge integration processes, like the one described in this work, are not free of obstacles Fernandez-Breis and Martínez-Béjar (2002), like preserving consistency and avoiding redundancy. Consistency can be further divided in data consistency and knowledge consistency. In terms of data consistency, the information from OMIM and the information from

¹⁸<http://jena.sourceforge.net/index.html>

¹⁹<http://www.mysql.com/>

²⁰<http://miuras.inf.um.es/ontologies/>

the most relevant advantages of the OGO system is the ability to identify a chain of relationships for querying the repository, so users are able to retrieve the information they are looking for in a short amount of time. Moreover, the query results are accurate since the information is annotated with the concepts in the ontology and query conditions can exploit the taxonomy of biological concepts like species (NCBI), evidence codes (ECO) or the biological process, cellular component and molecular function (GO) of orthologs.

The original OGO KB contained more than 90,000 ortholog clusters, more than a million genes, and *circa* a million proteins Miñarro Gimenez et al. (2009). As a result of the integration process, information about human genetic disorders was added to the OGO original KB, in the form of new instances: approximately 16,000 human genetic disorders and more than 17,000 references to PubMed citations. Therefore, in the new state of the OGO KB, for a particular gene, not only the information about its orthologous genes, but also the genetic disorders in which they are involved, can be retrieved. In the same manner, for a particular disease, not only the involved genes, but also the genes that are ortholog to them, from other organisms, can be retrieved.

An example of the queries that can be executed on the OGO repository can be seen in Figure 4. This query searches for human genetic diseases caused by genes that are orthologs of the gene ZFH2 and belong to the organism *Drosophila melanogaster*. The genetic diseases retrieved by the query read as follows: Prostate cancer, susceptibility to, 104155; Ptosis, congenital, 606940; Peroxisome biogenesis factor 12, 601758. This example shows some features of the potential of the OGO KB. It is possible to navigate from the relation between genetic diseases and genes to the relation of ortholog clusters in an intuitive manner. The query results were filtered by gene name and organism but they can also be filtered by GO terms, evidence codes or any other property that users may want to specify.

The repository is queried using SPARQL, a semantic language for querying RDF repositories. However, given that we cannot assume that biomedical researchers know this language, two different types of query interfaces have been developed: basic (Section 3.2) and advanced (Section 3.3). The basic type provides a text field to the users, so they can input the gene or disease of interest, and apply a series of filters. Such filters permit to limit the types of information to be part of the output (e.g., include/exclude the GO Terms associated to the genes), and to adjust the query (e.g., the genes of a particular organism). Given the translational nature of this repository, two versions

```

PREFIX ogo:<http://miuras.inf.um.es/ontologies/OGO.owl#>
PREFIX ncbi:<http://um.es/ncbi.owl#>
SELECT ?disease
WHERE
{
    ?disease    <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>    ogo:Disorder .
    ?disease    ogo:causedBy                                          ?gene .
    ?gene        <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>    ogo:Gene .
    ?cluster     ogo:hasOrthologous                                    ?gene .
    ?cluster     ogo:hasOrthologous                                    ?ortgene .
    ?ortgene     <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>    ogo:Gene .
    ?ortgene     <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#label>         "ZFH2" .
    ?ortgene     ogo:fromSpecies                                       ncbi:NCBI_7227 .
}

```

Figure 4: SPARQL query on OGO repository.

Figure 5: Web interface for searching orthologous clusters information: the gene ZFHX3.

of this basic query interface have been developed: one for those researchers who are interested in genes, and one for those interested in diseases as the starting point for their navigation and research.

3.2. Keyword-based Query Interface

The keyword-based query interface of the OGO System is shown in Figure 5. Two different perspectives were developed for searching the repository: gene-driven, and disorder-driven, which are described in subsections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2.

3.2.1. Gene-driven Query

This interface retrieves information of ortholog clusters and it is activated by selecting **orthology** in the combo box shown on top-left of the Figure 5, and its input is a gene name or an identifier. The retrieved information can also be filtered: organism which the gene is associated with, or the resource the gene was collected from. Moreover, some gene properties are optionally shown: alternative gene names, related proteins, the resources it can be found in, related GO terms and related genetic disorders. These attributes are retrieved by selecting the corresponding check-boxes. The user interface constitutes an extension of the one developed for the OGO repository, with the addition of the related genetic disorders. The interface uses a query pattern (Table 2) and the information provided by users for defining the user query. Thus, the *<KEYWORD>* corresponds to the gene name or ID. The query filters are the *<ORGANISM_n>*, which corresponds to any species in the NCBI taxonomy, and the *<RESOURCE_n>*, which corresponds to any orthologs repositories. The items between square brackets (*{?Disease}*, *{?Protein}*, *{?Name}*, *{?Resource}* and *{?GOterm}*) are related to the check-boxes which are available in this interface.

For example, if a user wants to search for information about the gene **ATBF1**, and the associated genetic disorders, all the check-boxes should be selected in the query interface and the name of the gene should be specified in the corresponding text area. Retrieved results consist of a list of orthologous gene records which belong to the same cluster. The gene record associated with **ATBF1** is shown in Figure 6. It contains the gene identifier, the name of its organism, the list of the other alternative gene aliases, the table with the names and identifiers of proteins, the list of information resources from which the genetic information was gathered, the list of genetic diseases, and the table of the corresponding GO terms, Evidence Codes and GOA associations that are related to it. Additional information about the items belonging to genes and genetic disorders can be accessed by clicking on its items.

3.2.2. Disease-driven Query

This interface provides information about genetic disorders and it is activated by selecting **OMIM** in the referred combo box. In this case, the user does not input the name or identifier of a gene, but an OMIM identifier or the name of a genetic disorder. When using OMIM identifiers in queries, exact matches are retrieved. On the other hand, using the name of a genetic disorder, all the disorders that contain any input word are retrieved. For

```

@prefix ogo: <http://miuras.inf.um.es/ontologies/OGO.owl>.
SELECT
  ?Gene0 ?Organism [?Disease ?Protein ?Name ?Resource ?GOTerm]
WHERE {
  ?Gene1 ogo:Name ?literal .
  FILTER (regex(?literal,<KEYWORD>)) .
  ?OrthologyCluster ogo:hasOrthologous ?Gene1 .
  ?OrthologyCluster ogo:hasOrthologous ?Gene0 .
  {
    ?Gene1 ogo:fromSpecies <ORGANISM1> .
    UNION
    ?Gene1 ogo:fromSpecies <ORGANISM2> .
    UNION
    ...
  }.
  {
    ?Gene1 ogo:hasResource <RESOURCE1> .
    UNION
    ?Gene1 ogo:hasResource <RESOURCE2> .
    UNION
    ...
  }.
  ?Gene0 ogo:fromSpecies ?Organism .
  [OPTIONAL { ?Disease ogo:causedBy ?Gene0 .}]
  [OPTIONAL { ?Gene0 ogo:translatedTo ?Protein .}]
  [OPTIONAL { ?Gene0 ogo:hasGO ?GOTerm .}]
  [OPTIONAL { ?Gene0 ogo:Name ?Name .}]
  [OPTIONAL { ?Gene0 ogo:hasResource ?Resource .}]
}

```

Table 2: Basic Orthologs query pattern.

each disease included in the results, the following information is provided: name, OMIM identifier, and link to the information about the disease. For example, if the user inputs **Prostate cancer** as the query, then the result is the list of genetic disorders shown in Figure 7.

On the other hand, if the user inputs an OMIM identifier, the information about that particular disease is shown. Thus, the interface uses the query pattern shown in Table 3 to define the query. The OMIM identifier replaces the *OMIMID* in the query. The items between brackets in the table (?Name, ?Location, ?DisorderReference, ?Gene, ?Disorder0, ?Method and ?Article) represent the properties and relationships values of a genetic disorder that are conceptualised in the KB. The example in Figure 8 shows the information retrieved when querying with the OMIM identifier 104155. The result includes the disorder name, the location of the gene in the genomic sequence, the list of alternative references to this genetic disease, the name of the gene (other gene aliases are also provided, *e.g.* zfhx3), the list of

Gene:		
ATBF1		
Organism:		
Homo sapiens		
Synonyms		
ID:463		
ATBT		
ZFHX3		
Protein Id	Protein Name	
118498345	NP_008816.3	
Resources		
Homologene		
Disorder		
Prostate cancer, susceptibility to [104155]		
GO Term	Evidence Code	GO Aspect
[GO:000122] negative regulation of transcription from RNA polymerase II promoter	IGI	Biological process
[GO:006355] regulation of transcription, DNA-dependent	TAS	Biological process
[GO:005667] transcription factor complex	IDA	Cellular component
[GO:005622] intracellular	IEA	Cellular component
[GO:005634] nucleus	TAS	Cellular component
[GO:008270] zinc ion binding	IEA	Molecular function
[GO:0043565] sequence-specific DNA binding	IEA	Molecular function
[GO:0046872] metal ion binding	IEA	Molecular function
[GO:0016564] transcription repressor activity	IGI	Molecular function
[GO:0003705] RNA polymerase II transcription factor activity, enhancer binding	TAS	Molecular function

Figure 6: Extract of the results for the gene ZFHX3.

Choose one of the record retrieved with "Prostate cancer" token :
Prostate cancer, susceptibility to [104155]
Prostate cancer, hereditary [153622]
Prostate cancer, hereditary, 13 [157145]
Prostate cancer 1, 176807 [180435]
Prostate cancer, hereditary,X-linked 1 [300147]
Prostate cancer, hereditary,X-linked 2 [300704]
Androgen insensitivity [313700]
Neurofibrosarcoma [600020]
Fanconi anemia, complementation group D1 [600185]
Prostate cancer, susceptibility to [600623]
Prostate cancer, progression and metastasis of [600997]
Bannayan-Riley-Ruvalcaba syndrome [601728]
Prostate cancer, progression of [601767]
Gastric cancer, somatic [602053]
Lymphoma,somatic [602686]
Prostate cancer, susceptibility to [602759]
Li-Fraumeni syndrome [604373]
Prostate cancer antigen 3 [604845]
Prostate cancer, susceptibility to [605367]
Prostate cancer aggressiveness QTL [607592]
Prostate cancer, susceptibility to, 3 [608656]
Prostate cancer, susceptibility to, 4 [608658]
Prostate cancer, hereditary, 5 [609299]
Prostate cancer, susceptibility to [609558]
Prostate cancer, hereditary, 12 [609922]
Prostate cancer, hereditary,7 [610321]
Prostate cancer, hereditary,9 [610997]
Prostate cancer, hereditary,10 [611100]
Prostate cancer, hereditary,11 [611955]
Prostate cancer, hereditary,14 [611958]
Prostate cancer, hereditary,15 [611959]
PC3 prostate cancer cell-secreted microprotein [612191]

Figure 7: Query example of a genetic disorder with the token Prostate cancer.

Search result with "104155" token :

Disease description:
Prostate cancer, susceptibility to [104155]
Location: 16q22.3-q23.1

Alternative disease names:
Prostate cancer, susceptibility to[176807]
Zinc finger homeobox 3

Gene:
ATBF1

Gene:
zfx3

Related omim records:
[176807]
Androgen insensitivity [313700]

Methods:
[D]: Deletion or dosage mapping (concurrency of chromosomal deletion and phenotypic evidence of hemizyosity), trisomy mapping (presence of three alleles in the case of a highly polymorphic locus), or gene dosage effects (correlation of trisomic state of part or all of a chromosome with 50% more gene product)
[A]: In situ DNA-RNA or DNA-DNA annealing

Pubmed Articles:
7592926
1719379

Figure 8: Query example of a genetic disorder with the identifier 104155.

other diseases that are associated to this disease, the list of methods used for linking genes to the disease, and the list of PubMed citations related to the disease. It is also possible to get more information about the gene, related diseases and articles by clicking on them.

```
@prefix ogo: <http://miuras.inf.um.es/ontologies/OGO.owl>.
SELECT
  ?Disorder [?Name ?Location ?DisorderReference ?Gene ?Disorder0 ?Method ?Article]
WHERE {
  ?Disorder ogo:OmimID <OMIMID> .
  [OPTIONAL { ?Disorder ogo:Name ?Name .}]
  [OPTIONAL { ?Disorder ogo:Location ?Location .}]
  [OPTIONAL { ?Disorder ogo:DisorderReference ?DisorderReference .}]
  [OPTIONAL { ?Disorder ogo:causedBy ?Gene .}]
  [OPTIONAL { ?Disorder ogo:connectedTo ?Disorder0 .}]
  [OPTIONAL { ?Disorder ogo:hasMethod ?Method .}]
  [OPTIONAL { ?Disorder ogo:relatedArticle ?Article .}]
}
```

Table 3: Basic Genetic Disorder query pattern.

3.3. Advanced Query Interface

The advanced interface allows users to perform a proper exploitation of the semantics of the repository by allowing the inclusion of concepts, proper-

ties and relationships of the OGO ontology in the queries, and it is activated by clicking on the **Advanced search** button. This interface assists users in defining advanced semantic queries. The query interface consists of three sub-modules: (1) query representation module; (2) guided search module; and (3) SPARQL coding module. The query representation module is responsible for storing the query clauses defined by the users through the web interface, and for ensuring the consistency of the query since it validates the values and conditions introduced. The guided search module guides users throughout the query definition stages. It assists users in the design of the query by enabling or disabling knowledge from the query ontology. Thus, only allowed query clauses are made available to users for (re) definition of such clauses. Finally, the corresponding SPARQL query is generated and issued.

For example, the design of the query “find all orthologs that belongs to *Rattus Norvegicus* and that are also related to the gene that causes **Prostate Cancer** ” is shown in Figure 9, and explained as follows:

1. Query concepts. In this case, we want to retrieve information about genetic diseases and their related genes. So, in order to add these concepts we have to click on the **Select Concept** button in the main interface and choose the Disorder and Gene classes from the hierarchy of classes available in the ontology to query (Figure 10). Then, **Disorder[0]** and **Gene[1]** appear in the **Search for** text area. The numbers in brackets identify different possible instances of the same class. So, **Gene[1]** and **Gene[2]** do not have to represent the same instance of Gene class.
2. Query constraints. The filters to be applied on the knowledge base appear in the text area **Query Requirement**. The **Add requirements** button allows to add them by showing the possible properties that can be used given the context of the requirements. The context is defined by the previously defined constraints and the selected query concepts. Figure 11 shows the allowed requirements for **Gene[1]** in the first phase of the query definition. Table 4 shows the user-defined query with the suitable requirements.
3. Query generation. Finally, the corresponding SPARQL query is generated by pressing the **Execute query** button. Table 5 shows the SPARQL query related to user-defined query in Table 4.

The results of the query (see Figure 12) are displayed in tabular form. Each column represents the ontology classes selected in the first step of query

Figure 9: User-defined Guided Query interface.

Figure 10: Hierarchy of classes which are made available for defining an advanced query.

Figure 11: Example of available requirements that can be chosen.

<p>Search for: Disorder[0] Gene[0]</p> <p>Query requirements: Disorder[0] → Name → “Prostate cancer“ Disorder[0] → causedBy → Gene[2] Cluster[3] → hasOrthologous → Gene[2] Cluster[3] → hasOrthologous → Gene[1] Gene[1] → fromSpecies → “Rattus Norvegicus“</p>
--

Table 4: Example of user-defined guided query.

definition. In this case, the results are two genetic disorders and some genes that are shown grouped by the corresponding genetic disorder.

<pre> @prefix ogo: <http://miuras.inf.um.es/ontologies/OGO.owl>. @prefix ncbi: <http://miuras.inf.um.es/ontologies/OGO.owl>. SELECT ?Disorder[0] ?Gene[1] WHERE ?Gene[1] ogo:fromSpecies ncbi:NCBI_10116 . ?Disorder[0] ogo:Name ?literal[4] . FILTER (regex (?literal[4], "Prostate cancer")) . ?Disorder[0] ogo:causedBy ?Gene[2] . ?Cluster[3] ogo:hasOrthologous ?Gene[2] . ?Cluster[3] ogo:hasOrthologous ?Gene[1] . } </pre>

Table 5: Example of SPARQL query corresponding to Table 4.

The grammar describing the SPARQL query capabilities offered by the advanced query interface is depicted in Table 6. It should be noted that the automatically generated SPARQL queries are optimized in order to reduce the response time. In terms of optimization, we sort the different types of condition clauses to make the SPARQL queries run faster. The sorting takes into account the details of our KB (it contains few concepts and relationships compared to the number of its instances). Thus, conditions which contain fewer variables and better fix a single individual are planned to be executed first and during the sorting phase.

4. Discussion and conclusions

In this work, medical data (human genetic diseases) and biological data (orthologs clusters) were integrated and semantically represented in the OGO system. The starting point for this work was our previous research, resulting

Disorder[0]	Gene[1]
104155, prostate cancer, susceptibility to, zinc finger homeobox 3	pex12, 116718
	rgd1560268, zfhx3.predicted, 307829
	rgd1563022, zfhx4.predicted, 310250
600020, neurofibrosarcoma, prostate cancer, susceptibility to, max-interacting protein 1	clec5a, 679787
	ensrnog00000026306, loc684510
	loc689617, 689617
	loc689629, 689629
	max, mgc124611, 60661
	mx1.wr, mx1, 25701
	tgap1, 294892

Figure 12: Result of the advanced query example of Table 4.

in an integrated semantic KB about orthology, the original OGO system. We reused the methodological approach described in Miñarro Gimenez et al. (2009) to process the extant knowledge about genetic diseases, and add it to the original KB, by improving and extending the original OGO ontology. Such extension was performed by adding new concepts and relationships about the domain of human genetic disorders to the OGO ontology. Given that both domains (human genetic disorders and orthologs clusters) are independent, the integration was free of inconsistencies and only the definition and execution of the mapping rules was necessary. The consistency of the integrated information is tested by defining domain restrictions and performing automated reasoning in order to verify its satisfaction. Therefore, this result contributes to consolidate our methodological approach, and the addition of new resources into OGO would require the execution of the same steps.

The OGO system has been built using the Semantic Web standards RDF, SPARQL and OWL. Specifically, by codifying the information in OWL, automated reasoning was exploited as a mechanism for the automatic validation of the information. Therefore, the OGO integration process can facilitate consistency, *e.g.* detecting a genetic disorder which is not related to any gene; and non-redundancy, *e.g.* detecting whether a gene has already

<p>Query ::= "SELECT" ListVar (WhereClause) ? ListVar ::= Var (Var) * WhereClause ::= "WHERE" { ConditionClause (ConditionClause) * } ConditionClause ::= [VarCondition LiteralCondition] "." VarCondition ::= [Var Individual] Property [Var Individual] LiteralCondition ::= [Var Individual] Property Var "." FILTER ("regex" (Var "," Literal)) Var ::= This term represents a variable in the query which can be matched to any resource of the ontology. Individual ::= This term represents a concept or individual identified by an URI in the ontology. Property ::= This term represents a relationship or property identified by an URI in the ontology. Literal ::= This term represents a literal value such as STRING, INTEGER, ...</p>

Table 6: Subset of SPARQL Grammar.

been integrated in the KB with the same name and belonging to the same species. Hence, OWL allows the integration of the additional information and resources like ECO, GO, NCBI and RO. By replacing our defined ontology concepts and relationships with those from the bio-ontologies mentioned above, the interconnection of disparate knowledge is facilitated. Sharing a common vocabulary that prevents definitions of ambiguous terms and reusing consolidated bio-ontologies help life scientists to understand the knowledge and to use it properly.

The standardization of the OGO ontology required the usage of the punning technique, which does not only allows for using the same URI for a class and an individual, but also provides the possibility of choosing whether to exploit OWL semantics on DL queries or directly exploit SPARQL queries (without having to use the OWL syntax for *e.g.* restrictions) in the same system. For example, as previously mentioned, in transitive composite queries like `participates_in some (part_of some cellular_process)`, due to OWL inference, both classes and individuals along `part_of` will be returned. On the other hand, in SPARQL efficient queries against OWL individuals like `?x participates_in cell_cycle`, the direct OWL individuals will be returned. In summary, punning is used in the OGO system for: (1) Incorporate OBO format bio-ontologies into the system "as is", using the standard translation from OBO to OWL, and yet be able to exploit SPARQL queries in a straight manner. As a result, other bio-ontologies, *e.g.* CL and its cross-products against GO²², can be integrated in the system, also "as is", been able to exploit even more knowledge; (2) Prospective DL queries over the

²²http://wiki.geneontology.org/index.php/XP:cellular_component_xp_cell

whole KB exploiting inference.

In the introduction section, we described the actions a researcher had to perform in order to retrieving the genes related to those that cause **Prostate cancer**. Using OGO, the researcher would only need to input **Prostate cancer** in order to receive the gene that causes the disease and, by click on the gene, its orthologs would be retrieved. Therefore, the OGO system is facilitating the work of researchers since the integration and comparison of information regarding orthologs and genetic diseases can be carried out automatically. By proceeding in this way, the researchers do not need to know anything about the structure and embedded meaning of the biomedical resources, since the OGO system makes it transparent.

RDF and SPARQL provide an efficient mechanism for querying semantic information, but users should not be required to learn semantic query languages for exploiting semantic repositories. In fact, Semantic Web researchers have noticed that “the casual user is typically overwhelmed by the formal logic of the Semantic Web” Bernstein and Kaufmann (2006). This is due to the fact that users, in order to use ontologies, have to be familiar with Wang et al. (2007): (1) the ontology syntax (*e.g.* RDF, OWL), (2) some formal query language (*e.g.* SPARQL), and (3) the structure and vocabulary of the target ontology. Consequently, alternative query methods are required.

Biomedical researchers are familiar with keyword-based query interfaces, because they follow the query pattern used in many available tools. This type of query interface is also provided by the OGO system, even though such interfaces exploit the domain semantics in a very limited way. Keyword-based interfaces offer fewer levels of freedom than user-based guided query definition. Otherwise, the higher levels of freedom users have, the fewer user-friendly interface is because of query semantic language complexity. Some semantic systems provide fully semantic user interfaces, but they are rather unpractical and not usable by non-expert users. Consequently, developing an advanced query interface that did not require biomedical researchers to master semantic languages was a challenge in this work. In this sense, our advanced interface allows users to properly exploit the semantics of the repository by allowing the inclusion of concepts, properties and relationships of the OGO ontology in the queries. Users are not required to write SPARQL queries, but to navigate over the OGO ontology, in order to exploit the semantics of the system.

In both types of interfaces provided by the OGO system (basic and advanced), the interface uses a query pattern that defines the types of queries

that can be designed by the user (e.g., gene name, gene identifier, disease name or disease identifier). Hence, the pattern is filled out with the information provided by the users in the text areas and check-boxes of the query interface and the corresponding SPARQL queries are generated. The current implemented SPARQL capabilities are a subset of the potential SPARQL expressivity. For instance, a subset of features, such as OR and NOT, has not yet been implemented in the interface. Besides, some axioms defined in the ontology, such as cardinality or disjointness, and properties such as label or comment are not allowed to be queried. These limitations simplify the query definition and thus provide users with only the elements of the ontology containing information about the domain.

To the best of our knowledge, there is not a system similar to the OGO system; the OGO system is a pioneering effort in the automatic integration of orthology and genetic diseases. However, even though the OGO system is a useful resource for exploring orthologs/disorders information in an integrated setting, the system can be technically improved in some areas. Even though efficient DL reasoning on KBs of the size of OGO will be possible in the short term, it is not practical currently, but the semantics of the system will be ready to exploit DL queries when reasoning becomes more efficient. The OGO KB does not allow to take advantage of the whole semantics provided by the imported bio-ontologies, as OWL queries could not be applied due to the size of the system. However, it is likely that automated reasoning will be possible in the short term²³, and, since the imported bio-ontologies are already part of the system, OWL queries exploiting inference should be able to be applied by simply increasing the efficiency of the system, without changing any semantic content. Also in the area of optimization, the OGO system can be extended with the Pellet Integrity Constraint Validator (Pellet ICV)²⁴. Pellet ICV interprets OWL ontologies by applying the Closed World Assumption, offering an efficient mechanism for using OWL as a schema language for validating information codified in RDF. Therefore, Pellet ICV offers a solution for checking the information gathered into the OGO system. Other extensions are planned for the OGO system. In terms of content, the OGO ontology can be extended with other bio-ontologies that also use

²³One of the OWL 2 profiles, OWL 2 QL (http://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-profiles/#OWL_2_QL), optimizes query answering for KBs with a high number of instances, like the OGO KB.

²⁴<http://clarkparsia.com/pellet/icv>

RO, effectively integrating such bio-ontologies with the bio-ontologies already present in the OGO system, enriching it.

In summary, the OGO system combines orthologs and human genetic diseases information, exploiting Semantic Web standards, to add value to those two types of information, by combining them. Therefore, the OGO system should be of interest, and save time, to any scientist interested in such intersection of knowledge domains.

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